

Estimation of Submicrogram Quantities of Ruthenium(III) by Catalysis of the Cerium(IV)-Ethanol Reaction in Aqueous Sulphuric Acid Media

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A catalytic kinetic method of estimation has some major limitations in practice compared to many other convenient methods (e.g. spectrophotometric method) but such methods¹ are important for the trace or ultra-trace quantities of different elements in which range the elements cannot be estimated spectrophotometrically or by any other convenient method (except such ultra-sensitive method as neutron activation). In the title reaction, Ru^{III} can potentially catalyse in the concentration range of 10⁻⁸ g ml⁻¹ and from the knowledge of dependence of the rate on the [Ru^{III}] in that range, Ru^{III} in solution can be estimated.

Results and Discussion

The uncatalysed cerium(IV)-ethanol reaction in the presence of excess substrate leading to quantitative oxidation of ethanol (i.e. 2 Ce⁴⁺ + C₂H₅OH → 2 Ce³⁺ + CH₃CHO + 2 H⁺) in aqueous sulphuric acid media is very slow but in the presence of Ru^{III} as a catalyst in the concentration range of 10⁻⁸ g ml⁻¹, the process becomes measurably fast² to be followed by conventional techniques like spectrophotometric or titrimetric method. In presence of excess ethanol in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid media, the rate of disappearance of cerium(IV) in the title reaction increases sharply with increasing [C₂H₅OH] to a value independent of [C₂H₅OH] over a large range (0.2–1.0 mol dm⁻³) in which the rate law conforms to

$$\frac{-2.303 \, d \log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{Ru}]_{\text{T}}$$

where $k_{\text{cat}} (= k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]^{-1})$ is a constant at a fixed JICS-10

sulphuric acid concentration, [Ru]_T gives the total ruthenium(III) concentration. The value of 10⁻³ k_{cat} at 30° in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid media is 1.7 ± 0.1 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹. In the ethanol concentration range where the process is zero order with respect to the substrate, the plot (Fig. 1) of k_{obs} vs [Ru]_T at a fixed [H₂SO₄] gives a straight-line passing through the origin, indicating nonexistence of the uncatalysed path under the experimental conditions. The plot can be taken as the reference curve from which the unknown concentration of ruthenium(III) can be estimated from

Fig. 1 Dependence of k_{obs} on [Ru^{III}] in the oxidation of ethanol by Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulphuric acid media: (A) 40°, (B) 30° and (C) 25°, [Ce^{IV}] = 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [C₂H₅OH] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, $l = 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (H₂SO₄ + NaClO₄)

the knowledge of k_{obs} .

Experimental

Standard stock solution of Ru^{III} was prepared³ from $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Johnson and Mathey). The Ce^{IV} stock solution was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium sulphate (G.R., E. Merck) in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid and standardised with iron(II) ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator. Ethanol was redistilled and its concentration was obtained from its density measurement⁴. All other reagents used were of reagent grade. A Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer was used to follow the process.

Procedure : The reaction was initiated by mixing the pre-equilibrated reactant solutions taken at the desired condition and the progress of the reaction was monitored by measuring the concentration of cerium(IV) remaining unreacted either spectrophotometrically at 320 nm ($\epsilon = 5.5 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) or titrimetrically using a known amount of excess standard ferrous ammonium sulphate and back-titrating

the unreacted ferrous ions against standard cerium(IV) solution using ferroin as an indicator. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was calculated as usual from the rate of disappearance of cerium(IV). Then the reference curve, k_{obs} vs $[\text{Ru}]_{\text{T}}$ was obtained.

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References

1. K. B. YAITSIMIRSKII, "Kinetic Method of Analysis", Pergamon, London, 1966; R. D. SAUERBRUNN and E. B. SANDLII, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1953, 22; C. SURASII and E. B. SANDLII, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1960, 22, 261.
2. A. K. DAS and M. DAS, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1995, 27, 7.
3. A. K. DAS and M. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 589.
4. M. ARDON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1811.